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- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
- 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
- 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
- 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
- 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
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INCORPORATION OF MOOCS INTO THE DIGITAL EDUCATIONAL FRAMEWORK FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF PROFESSIONAL SPEECH CULTURE

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Abstract: The establishment of a university's digital infrastructure is an essential prerequisite for the implementation of contemporary online education. The transition to distance education during the COVID-19 pandemic revealed significant challenges related to access to electronic educational materials and the improvement of modern instructional technologies. This study provides a scientific and methodological rationale for the use of the author's Massive Open Online Course (MOOC) "Professional Speech Culture" as a tool for online learning and remote support in the communicative and speech training of philology students.

The research analyzes the educational processes of undergraduate philology students at Mordovia State University during the period 2019–2021, with MOOCs employed as electronic educational resources. The study applies theoretical methods, including a review of scientific literature, as well as empirical methods such as observation of online courses within the frameworks of the Flipped Classroom and Blended Learning models, student surveys, and data analysis.

The theoretical significance of the study lies in substantiating the integration of a specialized MOOC to enhance communicative training. Its practical significance is associated with the development of an accessible electronic resource aimed at practice-oriented instruction. The findings demonstrate both the advantages and limitations of MOOCs as multimedia tools in flipped and blended learning environments and identify prospects for their further improvement.

Key words: linguistic culture; MOOC; online education; distance learning; blended learning; flipped classroom.

Annotatsiya: Universitetning raqamli infratuzilmasini shakllantirish zamonaviy onlayn ta'limni joriy etishning muhim sharti hisoblanadi. COVID-19 pandemiyasi davrida masofaviy ta'limga o'tish elektron ta'lim resurslaridan foydalanish imkoniyati hamda zamonaviy o'qitish texnologiyalarini takomillashtirish bilan bog'liq muammolarni yaqqol namoyon etdi. Ushbu tadqiqot mualliflik asosida ishlab chiqilgan "Professional nutq madaniyati" ommaviy ochiq onlayn kursidan (MOOK) filologiya yo'nalishi talabalarini uchun kommunikativ va nutqiy tayyorgarlikni rivojlantirishda onlayn ta'lim va masofaviy qo'llab-quvvatlash vositasi sifatida foydalanishning ilmiy-uslubiy asoslarini yoritadi.

Tadqiqotda 2019–2021-yillar davomida Mordoviya davlat universiteti filologiya yo'nalishi bakalavriat talabalarining ta'lim jarayonlari MOOKlar elektron ta'lim resursi sifatida qo'llanilgan holda tahlil qilindi. Ilmiy adabiyotlar tahliliga asoslangan nazariy yondashuvlar hamda teskari sinf va aralash ta'lim modellari doirasida onlayn kurslarni kuzatish, talabalar o'rtasida so'rovnomalarni o'tkazish va olingan ma'lumotlarni tahlil qilish kabi empirik metodlardan foydalanildi.

Tadqiqotning nazariy ahamiyati kommunikativ tayyorgarlikni rivojlantirishda maxsus MOOKlarni integratsiyalash zarurligini asoslab berishda namoyon bo'ladi. Amaliy ahamiyati esa amaliyotga yo'naltirilgan ta'limni ta'minlovchi qulay elektron resursni yaratish bilan belgilanadi. Tadqiqot natijalari MOOKlarning teskari va aralash ta'lim jarayonlaridagi afzalliklari va cheklovlarini aniqlab, ularni takomillashtirish istiqbollari belgilaydi.

Kalit so'zlar: lingvistik madaniyat; MOOK; onlayn ta'lim; masofaviy ta'lim; aralash ta'lim; teskari sinf.

Аннотация: Формирование цифровой инфраструктуры университета является необходимым условием реализации современного онлайн-образования. Переход к дистанционному обучению в период пандемии COVID-19 выявил проблемы доступности электронных образовательных материалов и необходимость совершенствования современных образовательных технологий. В статье представлено научно-методическое обоснование использования авторского массового открытого онлайн-курса “Культура профессиональной речи” в качестве средства онлайн-обучения и дистанционной поддержки коммуникативно-речевой подготовки студентов филологического профиля.

В исследовании проанализированы образовательные процессы студентов бакалавриата филологического направления Мордовского государственного университета за период 2019–2021 годов с применением MOOC в качестве электронных образовательных ресурсов. Используются теоретические методы, включая анализ научной литературы, а также эмпирические методы: наблюдение за онлайн-курсами в рамках моделей перевернутого класса и смешанного обучения, анкетирование студентов и анализ полученных данных.

Теоретическая значимость исследования заключается в обосновании интеграции специализированных MOOC для повышения уровня коммуникативной подготовки. Практическая значимость связана с разработкой доступного электронного ресурса, ориентированного на практико-ориентированное обучение. Результаты исследования демонстрируют преимущества и ограничения MOOC как мультимедийных инструментов в условиях перевернутого и смешанного обучения, а также определяют перспективы их дальнейшего совершенствования.

Ключевые слова: лингвистическая культура; MOOC; онлайн-образование; дистанционное обучение; смешанное обучение; перевернутый класс.

INTRODUCTION

Digital pedagogy, a fundamental component of the contemporary shift in education toward globalization, refers to the use of digital technologies and Internet resources to create an open and accessible educational environment. Ogarev Mordovia State University has actively participated in the digitization of educational services within the framework of the “Modern Digital Educational Environment in the Russian Federation” project implemented during 2016–2021.

The university’s electronic information and educational environment (EIEE), including Massive Open Online Courses (MOOCs), facilitates students’ access to education regardless of geographical constraints, thereby promoting flexible approaches to the development of professional competencies. The epidemic accelerated the expansion of distance learning, revealing discrepancies between educational demands and the availability of digital resources and subject-specific expertise.

The significance of this study is driven by the growing need for a systematic understanding of contemporary methodologies in the development and implementation of online educational resources.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Distance education technologies and interaction models have been documented since their early development (Higgins & Johns, 1984; Shchennikov, 2002; Clark & Mayer, 2011). Over the past decade, the modeling and integration of Massive Open Online Courses (MOOCs) have emerged as key topics of academic discourse (Evans & Myrick, 2015; Grechushkina, 2018).

Analysis of computer-assisted language learning (CALL) demonstrates that online language training courses offer additional resources for enhancing communicative skills, particularly in distance-learning formats. Nevertheless, the specific strategies for integrating such courses into the practical curriculum of language-related disciplines remain insufficiently defined.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The study focused on the Massive Open Online Course (MOOC) “Professional Speech Culture”, developed by the staff of the Department of Russian as a Foreign Language at Mordovia State University. The course is delivered through the regional “Ogarev University” platform and the “Pushkin Online” platform.

Structure of Course Content

The course consists of modules addressing lexical standards, grammatical norms, and functional styles, including Scientific, Conversational, Publicistic, and Official–Business styles. Each module comprises video lectures (5–6 videos, each with a duration of 6–11 minutes), control blocks consisting of practical assignments and module-based assessments, as well as a final evaluation conducted through supervised testing.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Outcomes and Examination

Survey findings obtained from 48 students (25 native speakers and 23 foreign students) indicated that 100 % of native speakers experienced no technical difficulties, whereas 58 % of international students reported intermittent connection problems.

Seventy-one percent of respondents reported prompt access to learning resources, sixty-three percent expressed satisfaction with multimedia content, and forty-three percent positively evaluated the individualized work plan.

Retention. The module “Conversational Style: The Physician–Patient Dialogue” was identified as the most memorable by more than 50 % of respondents in both groups, which can be attributed to its professional relevance and originality.

Human Element. Despite the identified advantages, 56 % of native speakers and 83 % of foreign students stated that online courses cannot fully replace face-to-face instruction due to the lack of live communication and immediate feedback.

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

Digital education has become an established reality. MOOCs provide broad educational accessibility and support personalized learning pathways. The overall effectiveness of such educational formats largely depends on the instructor’s ability to balance and manage student learning activities. This aspect is particularly critical in speech culture disciplines, where a high level of active verbal engagement must be consistently maintained. Future research should focus on achieving an optimal balance between asynchronous and synchronous forms of communication in order to enhance communicative and speech competencies within blended learning frameworks.

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 - 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
 - 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
 - 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
 - 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
 - 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
 - 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
 - 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
 - 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
 - 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
 - 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

MAKTABGACHA VA MAKTAB TA'LIMI

Mas'ul muharrir: Ramzidin Ashurov

Ingliz tili muharriri: Murod Xoliyorov

Musahhih: Alibek Zokirov

Sahifalovchi va dizayner: Iskandar Islomov

2026. №1

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"Maktabgacha va maktab ta'limi" jurnali 26.09.2023-yildan O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Adminstratsiyasi huzuridagi Axborot va ommaviy kommunikatsiyalar agentligi tomonidan №C-5669363 reyestr raqami tartibi bo'yicha ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.
Litsenziya raqami: № 136361.

Manzirimiz: Toshkent shahar, Yunusobod tumani
19-mavze, 17-uy.